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Project title: COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production

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Deliverable D5.3 - Project Website

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WP5 - Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Activities

WP leader - BRAINPORT

PROJECT TITLE

COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards Era-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production

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Executive Summary

This deliverable D5.3, entitled "Project website", aims to showcase the layout of the COOPERATE project website consistent with the graphic style of the logo. The COOPERATE project website - developed in month 2- is an essential communication channel for the project. It will host tools for interacting with stakeholders and ecosystems, documents and materials produced as part of the COOPERATE methodology, news, information, events, and results, and simplify communication with the general public. The website will be continuously updated to ensure the achievement of all goals, including the incorporation of a dedicated page for digital tools. It will serve as a living tool, updated to reflect developments and results achieved during the project and enable interactions with stakeholders to exchange on the ERA Hub concept.

The project website link is <https://cooperate-project.eu>, where the most important results of the project will be published and presented in a clear and understandable format. The website content includes information on the ERA Hub concept, the COOPERATE project's overall objectives, and the main methods of internal and external communication, such as social media, newsletters, and press releases. The project website aims to address various target audiences, including researchers, scientific experts, industry practitioners, ecosystems partners, businesses, policy makers, and the community at large, providing easy navigation through dedicated sections of the site, accessing valuable information related to the COOPERATE project. This public website will present the project brand over time and provide well-presented and non-confidential information on the project framework, consortium, related activities, project results, news and relevant events.

List of abbreviation/Nomenclature

ACRONYM	STANDS FOR
DX.X	Deliverable number
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
MX	Project Month number
TX.X	Task number
WP	Work Package

This document is a description of the website which is part of work package 5 (WP5) "Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Activities" of the COOPERATE project.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable is a critical component of the dissemination infrastructure for the COOPERATE project, providing a platform for communication between partners, stakeholders, the EC, and the general public. It includes all the necessary information related to project developments and tools, organized into dedicated sections.

The COOPERATE website will function as a knowledge hub, gathering all important project findings and data, such as studies and reports produced during the operational project work. It will also serve as an access point to the self-assessment digital tools and a repository for the tools and guidelines for all stakeholders involved in co-creation activities.

Regularly updated content will be generated and distributed at the EU level to enhance public awareness of the ERA-HUBs among citizens, public authorities, and stakeholders, with key, easy-to-understand, and targeted messages. These messages will be disseminated via multiple channels, including social media (LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube), e-newsletters (every three months about progress made, events and activities), press releases, videos, podcasts and communication kit (factsheets, flyers, and posters).

The website will also provide updates on the progress of the COOPERATE project on a regular basis and will be maintained and updated throughout the project's lifetime. The website's structure is flexible and easy to modify to accommodate partners' suggestions and the introduction of new sections as the project progresses.

Additionally, the website is designed to be responsive, adapting to the user's screen size, making it accessible on a wide range of devices, from smartphones to personal computers. The website is built with WordPress functionalities, including plug-ins for user question forms and newsletter subscriptions, which can be managed by the site/project administrator.

1.1 Structure of the Deliverable

To ensure comprehensive coverage of the topics introduced, this document has been structured as follows:

- Section 1 presents the general structure of the deliverable and its contents.
- Section 2 describes the methodology used for the development of the COOPERATE project website.
- Section 3 showcases the structure and features of the website, including its main sections and the tools and information available to users.
- Section 4 summarizes the key points covered in the document and presents conclusions regarding the importance of the COOPERATE project.

1.2 Relation to other Tasks and Deliverables

The website is a fundamental tool for disseminating all project information, feeds on the content of all technical work packages and, it is the first source of information for all stakeholders. Although the project website falls under WP5 (T5.1, T5.2, D5.3), it will be developed thanks to inputs received from all other work packages as well. In particular, WP1 will use the website to integrate the platform set-up to create the network of ERA Hubs along with self-assessment tools and compliance criteria. Moreover, WP3 concerns digital tools to attract and connect the stakeholders from EU ecosystems. The digital tools (D3.3, D3.4) will be integrated into the project website and will introduce a proactive layer towards stakeholders along their journey to become ERA Hubs, according to the guidelines developed in WP2. In relation to WP4, The website will host a 'Help Desk Space' to provide support to applicants and proactively present them the model and overall project ambition. A "Call for Champions" Toolkit will be elaborated and shared with all partners involved in CD activities (WP4, T4.2, D4.2). The campaign will include webinars dedicated to ecosystems with the involvement of local authorities call forand EC. A dedicated area for this campaign will be created in the project website.

2. Methodology

The COOPERATE project website was created with the aim of providing easy access to project information, tools, and results for various stakeholders, but also to be a living tool for ERA hubs. The website's design follows a simple and user-friendly approach, which was developed through collaborative efforts within the Consortium.

The website's structure resembles a pyramid, with a homepage that leads to categories, subcategories, news, hub tools, and pages. The website's main features were selected based on the following criteria:

- Accessibility and reach out: free general access, wide reach.
- Usability: easy content management, high flexibility of design and Usable/understandable content structure.
- Versatility: ability to publish multimedia content.
- Efficiency: low setup and maintenance costs.
- Compatibility and synergies: compatibility with communication channels used by project partners (institutional communication), potential for synergic communication.

The website was set up with the following methodology, which aligns with the project's goals:

- Increase general awareness of the project.
- Involve relevant stakeholders in selected project activities.
- Support cooperation with research partners outside the consortium.
- Disseminate important consortium activities and outcomes of the project.
- Facilitate access to ERA hubs.

3. COOPERATE Website

The COOPERATE project website can be found at <https://cooperate-project.eu> and serves as a comprehensive resource for information on the project, its objectives, and results for audiences worldwide. The ".eu" domain emphasizes the European nature and level of the project, while the EU logo, grant number, and funding statement appear in the website footer.

The COOPERATE website was launched in February 2023, during month 2 of the project. It is the primary platform for disseminating information on the project, with several key purposes, including:

- Providing official information on the project's motivation, objectives, technological approach, and work plan, as well as information on the consortium involved in the project.
- Serving as a public repository for institutional results, such as deliverables and interviews, as well as dissemination materials such as scientific papers, presentations, whitepapers, brochures, promotional videos, e-newsletters, workshop materials, and press releases.
- Disseminating news and events related to the project and its topics.
- Providing tools and guidelines to interested companies and organizations.
- Providing access to the platform to be developed.

The website will be regularly maintained and updated throughout the duration of the project and will remain active for at least two years following project completion.

3.1 Website features

The COOPERATE website is built on the WordPress platform, which offers a variety of useful tools and functionalities. The site administrator can access simple site access statistics through this platform.

The website design features a simple, user-friendly layout with a graceful font, blue tones, and a complementary accent color. It is built with a responsive design, making it accessible not only from computers, but also from mobile devices such as tablets and smartphones.

The design is consistent with the visual identity of the project, with a menu on the homepage leading users to the main features of the site (see below). To promote greater awareness and engagement with external stakeholders, the project website is complemented by a strong social media presence.

COOPERATE project

Figure 1 COOPERATE Website header

The structure of the website is described in detail hereafter. The home page shows some information about the project and contains an interactive menu that the user can navigate to access the following website sections:

- Home
- About
- Material hub
- News
- Partners
- Contacts

Menu items can be browsed through the main navigation bar at the top of the site. A new section on digital tools called Playbook and Toolbox will be added.

Below is information on the different subsections of the site.

Home

Leads to the landing page and shows the homepage of the project website.

Project Description

It contains a brief summary of the ERA Hubs concept and project objectives of defining and piloting the ERA Hubs in Europe.

About

A vibrant ecosystem is an essential condition for growth, and with COOPERATE the aim is to pilot the European Research Area (ERA)-Hub concept with a limited number of ecosystems and help provide a toolkit of best practices and activities that ensure a strong basis for a potential scale-up in different geographies across the EU territory in the next phase. COOPERATE will define the ERA Hubs concept through co-creation arenas gathering quadruple helix actors from

Figure 2 COOPERATE About header

Material Hub

This page will contain all the dissemination materials and open access documents developed during the project: it will give the public access to free downloads of COOPERATE fact sheets, e-newsletters, posters, videos and brochures.

In this section the ERA hub materials will be shared openly.

Material hub

Below you'll find news and additional material regarding COOPERATE and the ERA hub concept.

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Figure 3 COOPERATE Material hub header

News

This page presents updates and news about the COOPERATE project.

Figure 4 COOPERATE News header

Partners

In this category, the consortium is presented through the logo, company name and link to the official website of all partners.

Figure 5 COOPERATE Partners header

Contacts

This page contains the contact details of the project coordinator and the technical manager.

Contacts

COOPERATE overall objective is to develop and pilot the ERA Hub concept based on the vision and success stories developed within the EuroTech Universities Alliance and their R&I ecosystems. The overall approach revolves around co-creation Arenas in which ecosystems and a broader community of quadruple helix actors can interact.

Do not hesitate to contact us, you will find all useful information on

Figure 6 COOPERATE Contacts header

Figure 7 COOPERATE Home and About pages

COOPERATE

Material hub

Home | About | Material hub | News | Contact

What is PBA Hub?

COOPERATE is a platform for the development of a new generation of... (text continues)

PREVIOUS RELEASES

- 1. COOPERATE is a platform for the development of a new generation of...
- 2. COOPERATE is a platform for the development of a new generation of...

RELATED DOCUMENT

COOPERATE

Home | About | Material hub | News | Contact

COOPERATE

Home | About | Material hub | News | Contact

COOPERATE

Home | About | Material hub | News | Contact

OUR EVENTS

COOPERATE

COOPERATE is a platform for the development of a new generation of... (text continues)

COOPERATE is a platform for the development of a new generation of... (text continues)

Home | About | Material hub | News | Contact

Home | About | Material hub | News | Contact

Home | About | Material hub | News | Contact

COOPERATE

General Assembly Meeting in Lyngby, Denmark

Home | About | Material hub | News | Contact

COOPERATE is a platform for the development of a new generation of... (text continues)

COOPERATE to develop and pilot the ERA Hub concept in Europe: Kick off Meeting in Eindhoven, The Netherlands

Home | About | Material hub | News | Contact

COOPERATE is a platform for the development of a new generation of... (text continues)

Information about this site

Home | About | Material hub | News | Contact

Funded by the European Union

COOPERATE is a platform for the development of a new generation of... (text continues)

COOPERATE

Partners

Home | About | Material hub | News | Contact

TU/e

TU/e

TU/e

TU/e

TU/e

TU/e

TU/e

TU/e

Information about this site

Home | About | Material hub | News | Contact

Funded by the European Union

COOPERATE is a platform for the development of a new generation of... (text continues)

Contacts

COOPERATE is a platform for the development of a new generation of... (text continues)

CONTACT US

Home | About | Material hub | News | Contact

First name (required)

Last name (required)

Phone (required)

Company (required)

Country (required)

City (required)

State (required)

Zip (required)

Street (required)

Submit

Information about this site

Home | About | Material hub | News | Contact

Funded by the European Union

COOPERATE is a platform for the development of a new generation of... (text continues)

Figure 8 COOPERATE Other pages

3.2 Roles and Responsibilities for website management

All project partners are responsible for regularly and promptly providing relevant content to ensure the COOPERATE project website is consistently updated with news and information. Whenever contributions are requested, partners must provide information to the Coordinator for approval and the Work Package Leader BRAINPORT to upload within appropriate timelines.

Partners are also responsible for informing BRAINPORT about any news related to the project, and BRAINPORT will proactively ensure that the latest and best information is always available on the website. Additionally, all partners will publish news about their participation in the consortium and the COOPERATE project on their own websites and social media channels. This approach will inform their own ecosystems about their participation and create direct traffic to the COOPERATE website.

4. Conclusion

This deliverable describes the website that will be used to communicate the developments, results, and activities of the COOPERATE project to the world. The official project website will provide relevant information on COOPERATE to the public through posts, news items, and web pages. The website will also serve as an online repository of project results, such as publications, presentations, and other media, with corresponding documents accessible to the public.

The Playbook and Toolbox, which are crucial for the project's progress, will be added a few months after the project's start and will be among the most relevant parts of the project. The project's progress will be disseminated through the COOPERATE communication kit, which includes the general project presentation and project fact sheet. These materials, along with published newsletters, will be updated regularly to report effectively and comprehensively on the project's progress.